

JASMIN

Petascale storage and terabit networking for environmental science

Matt Pritchard

Centre for Environmental Data Archival
RAL Space

Jonathan Churchill

Scientific Computing Department

STFC Rutherford Appleton Laboratory

What is JAMSIN?

- What is it?
 - 16 Petabytes high-performance disk
 - 4000 computing cores
 - (HPC, Virtualisation)
 - High-performance network design
 - Private clouds for virtual organisations
- For Whom?
 - **Entire NERC community**
 - Met Office
 - European agencies
 - Industry partners
- How?

Context

JASMIN: the missing piece

- Urgency to provide better environmental predictions
- Need for higher-resolution models
- HPC to perform the computation
- Huge increase in observational capability/capacity

But...

- Massive storage requirement: observational data transfer, storage, processing
- Massive raw data output from prediction models
- Huge requirement to process raw model output into usable predictions (graphics/post-processing)

Hence JASMIN...

ARCHER supercomputer (EPSRC/NERC)

JASMIN (STFC/Stephen Kill)

Data growth

(Credit: Folkes, Churchill)

Light blue = total of all tape at STFC

Green = Large Hadron Collider (LHC) Tier 1 data on tape

Dark blue = data on **disk** in JASMIN

Data growth on JASMIN has been limited by:

Not enough disk (now fixed ...for a while)

Not enough local compute (now fixed ...for a while)

Not enough inbound bandwidth (now fixed ...for a while)

JASMIN

jasmin-login1

SSH login gateway

jasmin-xfer1

Data transfers

firewall

jasmin-sci1

Science/analysis

lotus.jc.rl.ac.uk

Batch processing cluster

Key:

 General-purpose resources

 Project-specific resources

 Data centre resources

Data Centre Archive

 /badc

 /neodc

User view

Success stories (1)

- QA4ECV
 - Re-processed MODIS Prior in 3 days on JASMIN-LOTUS, 81x faster than original process on 8-core blade
 - Throw hardware* at the problem

*Right type of hardware

Success stories (2)

- Test feasible resolutions for global climate models
- 250 Tb in 1 year generated on PRACE supercomputing facility in Germany (HERMIT). 400 Tb total.
- Network transfer to JASMIN
- Analysed by Met Office scientists as soon as available
- Deployment of VMs running custom scientific software, co-located with data
- Outputs migrated to long term archive (BADC)

Image: P-L Vidale & R. Schiemann, NCAS

Mizielinski et al ([Geoscientific Model Development, 2013](#))
“High resolution global climate modelling; the UPSCALE project, a large simulation campaign”

Coming soon

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News story

Europe's Earth observation programme maximised by UK data hub

From: UK Space Agency
First published: 24 March 2015
Part of: Science and innovation and UK economy

The UK is to host a world-class data facility, giving scientists full access to Earth observation data from Europe's Copernicus programme.

Signature of ESA/UK Collaborative Ground Segment Cooperation agreement.
Credit: ESA-N. Imbert-Vier, 2015.

Phase 2/3 expansion

- 2013 NERC Big Data capital investment
 - Wider scope: support projects from new communities, e.g.
 - EOS Cloud
 - Environmental 'omics. Cloud BioLinux platform
 - Geohazards
 - Batch compute of Sentinel-1a SAR for large-scale, hi-res Earth surface deformation measurement

Sentinel-1a (ESA)

	Phase 2 by March 2014	Phase 3 by March 2015
JASMIN hard upgrade	+7 Petabytes disk +6 Petabytes tape +3000 compute cores network enhancement	+o(2) Petabytes disk +o(800) compute cores network enhancement
JASMIN soft upgrade	Virtualisation software Scientific analysis software Cloud management software Dataset construction Documentation	

JASMIN Now

5+6.9+4.4 = 16.3 PB disk
Batch Compute
Host Compute

Phase 1 & 2 joined as part of Phase 3

JASMIN Analysis Platform

- Software stack for scientific analysis on JASMIN
 - Common packages for climate science, geospatial analysis
 - **CIS** developed as part of JASMIN
 - Deployed on JASMIN
 - Shared VMs
 - Sci VM template
 - LOTUS

Community Intercomparison Suite (CIS)

CIS = Component of JAP

Time-series

Line plots

Scatter plots

Global plots

Curtain plots

Overlay plots

Histograms

Dataset	Format
AERONET	Text
MODIS	HDF
CALIOP	HDF
CloudSAT	HDF
AMSRE	HDF
TRMM	HDF
CCI aerosol & cloud	NetCDF
SEVIRI	NetCDF
Flight campaign data	RAF
Models	NetCDF

Vision for JASMIN 2 (Applying lessons from JASMIN 1)

- Some key features
 - Nodes are general purpose: boot as bare metal or hypervisors
 - Use cloud tenancy model to make Virtual Organisations
 - Networking: made isolated network inside JASMIN to give users greater freedom: full IaaS, root access to hosts ...

JASMIN Cloud Architecture

First cloud tenants

- EOS Cloud
 - Environmental bio-informatics
- MAJIC
 - Interface to land-surface model
- NERC Environmental Work Bench
 - Cloud-based tools for scientific workflows

Consortia
Atmospheric & Polar Science
Archive
Earth Observation & Climate Services
Ecology & Hydrology
Genomics
Geology
NCAS CMS Director cross-cutting activities
Oceanography & Shelf Seas
Solid Earth & Mineral Physics

5+6.9+4.4=16.3 PB Disk

Batch Compute
Host Compute

Phase 1 and 2 were joined in
Phase 3

Panasas Storage

- Parallel file system (cf Lustre, GPFS, pNFS etc)
 - Single Namespace
 - 140GB/sec benchmarked (95 shelves PAS14)
 - Access via PanFS client/NFS/CIFS
 - Posix filesystem out of the box.
- Mounted on Physical machines and VMs
- 103 shelves PAS11
+ 101 shelves PAS14
+ 40 Shelves PAS16
 - Each shelf connected at 10Gb (20Gb PAS14)
 - 2,684 'Blades'
 - Largest single realm & single site in the world
- One Management Console
- TCO: *Big Capital, Small Recurrent*
but JASMIN2 £/TB < GPFS/Lustre offerings

Three year growth pains

172.16.144.0/21 = 2,000 IPs

130.246.136.0/21

Flat Overlaid L2

160->240 Ports @ 10Gb

RAL Jasmin/CEMS Gnodal Physical Topology

RAL Jasmin/CEMS Gnodal Physical Topology Installed July 2012

4 x VMware Clusters

vJASMIN
156 cores, 1.2TB

40x 10Gb

NetApp+Dell 1010TB +
(VM VMDK images)

32x 10Gb

vCloud
208-1648 cores,
1.5TB – 12.8TB

40x 10Gb

Panasas Storage
20PBytes
15.1 PB (usable)

385 x 10Gb

468 x 10Gb

A network :
1,100 Ports @ 10GbE

Overview

*£12.5M, 38 Racks,
850Amps, 25 tonnes,
3Terabit/s bandwidth*

Lotus HPC Cluster

MPI network
(10Gb low latency eth)

144-234 hosts, 2.2K-3.6K cores.
RHEL6, Platform LSF, MPI

Network Design Criteria

- Non-Blocking (No network contention)
- Low Latency ($< 20\mu\text{S}$ MPI. Preferably $< 10\mu\text{S}$)
- Small latency spread.
- Converged (IP storage, SAN storage, Compute, MPI)
- 700-1100 Ports @ 10Gb
- Expansion to 1,600 ports and beyond wo forklift.
- Easy to manage and configure
- Cheap
- later on:
Replaces JASMIN1 240 ports in place.

Floor Plan
Network distributed ~30m x ~20m

JASMIN 1

JASMIN 4,5
(2016-20) ...

JASMIN 3

JASMIN 2

Science DMZ

Cabling Costs: Central Chassis Switch + ToR

312 Twinax

Fully Populated ToR

6x S4810 ToR Switches
48x Active Optic QSFP

1:1 Contention ToR

20x S4810 ToR Switches
80x Active Optic QSFP

ToR e.g Force10 S4810P
48 x 10Gb SFP+
4x 40Gb QSFP+

1,000 Fibre Connections = £400-600K
JASMIN1+2 700-1100 10Gb Connections

Lots of core 40Gb ports needed.
MLAG to 72 Ports ?....
Chassis switch ? ... expansion/cost

ECMP Core

1,104 x 10GbE Ports CLOS L3 ECMP OSPF

- 768 Ports max. no expansion ... so 12 spines
- Max 36 leaf switches :1,728 Ports @ 10GbE
- Non-Blocking. Zero Contention (48x10Gb = 12x 40Gb uplinks)
- Low Latency (250nS L3 / per switch/router). 7-10uS MPI
- Cheap ! (ish)

RAL Site Network (for comparison)

ECMP CLOS L3 Advantages

- Massive scale
- Low cost (Pay as you grow)
- High performance
- Low latency
- Standards based – supports multiple vendors
- Very small “blast radius” upon network failures
- Small isolated subnets
- Deterministic latency with a fixed spine and leaf

<https://www.nanog.org/sites/default/files/monday.general.hanks.multistage.10.pdf>

ECMP CLOS L3 Issues

- Managing scale:
 - #s of IPs, subnets, VLANs, Cables
 - Monitoring
- Routed L3 network:
 - Reqs dynamic OSPF routing (100's routes per switch)
 - No L2 between switches (VMware: SAN's, vMotion)
 - Reqs: DHCP Relay, VXLAN
 - Complex 'traceroute' seen by users.

IP and Subnet Management

4 IPs / Cable

- 2x /21 Panasas Storage
- 4x /24 Internet Connects
- 55x /26 Fabric Subnets
- 264x /30 Inter switch links
- 514 VMs & Growing quickly
- 304 Servers, 850 Switches/PDUs etc
- 2,684 Storage Blades
- ~260 VLAN IDs
- 6,000 IPs & Growing

Monitoring / Visualisation

- Complex Cacti
 - >30 Fabric Switches
 - >50 Mgmt Switches
- 100's links to monitor
- Nagios bloat


```
root@host052:~  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]# ping mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk  
PING mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk (172.16.151.121) 56(84) bytes of data.  
64 bytes from mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk (172.16.151.121): icmp_seq=1 ttl=60  
64 bytes from mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk (172.16.151.121): icmp_seq=2 ttl=60  
64 bytes from mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk (172.16.151.121): icmp_seq=3 ttl=60  
^C  
--- mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk ping statistics ---  
3 packets transmitted, 3 received, 0% packet loss, time 2142ms  
rtt min/avg/max/mdev = 0.067/0.138/0.230/0.068 ms  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]# Four routed ECMP hops  
[root@host052 ~]#  
[root@host052 ~]# traceroute -I mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk  
traceroute to mgmt.jc.rl.ac.uk (172.16.151.121), 30 hops max, 60 byte packets  
1 26.64.1) 0.437 ms 0.468 ms 0.485 ms  
2 18.109.5) 0.401 ms 0.406 ms 0.417 ms  
3 18.103.66) 0.387 ms 0.409 ms 0.425 ms  
4 18.224.1) 0.248 ms 0.381 ms 0.517 ms  
5 (172.16.151.121) 0.107 ms 0.115 ms 0.115 ms  
[root@host052 ~]#
```

Fast

Implications of L3 CLOS for Virtualisation

- VXLAN Overlays
- Multicast routing → PIM
- Panasas access still direct
- Routed iSCSI
- # Subnets
- Sub-optimal IP use

The need for speed

LOTUS Cumulative # Jobs

Further info

- JASMIN
 - <http://www.jasmin.ac.uk>
- Centre for Environmental Data Archival
 - <http://www.ceda.ac.uk>
- JASMIN paper

Lawrence, B.N. , V.L. Bennett, J. Churchill, M. Jukes, P. Kershaw, S. Pascoe, S. Pepler, M. Pritchard, and A. Stephens. **Storing and manipulating environmental big data with JASMIN.** *Proceedings of IEEE Big Data 2013*, p68-75, [doi:10.1109/BigData.2013.6691556](https://doi.org/10.1109/BigData.2013.6691556)

